

PFAS, PCBs, PCDD/Fs, PAHs and extractable organic fluorine in bio-based fertilizers, amended soils and plants: exposure assessment and temporal trends

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1 Information about BBFs

Crystallisation

ID:	CGO
Waste origin:	Wastewater supernatant
Valorization method:	Struvite precipitation
N:	10.2 %
P:	22.8 %
K:	-
DM content:	55.4 %
Max application rate:	1.7 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

Incineration

ID:	EPH
Waste origin:	Sunflower husk ash
Valorization method:	Incineration and pelletising
N:	0.13 %
P:	1.95 %
K:	25-31 %
DM content:	96.5 %
Max application rate:	2.6 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on P-content)

ID:	PLA
Waste origin:	Poultry litter ash
Valorization method:	Incineration
N:	0.01
P:	5.23 %
K:	-
DM content:	92.8 %
Max application rate:	1.0 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on P-content)

ID:	ADC
Waste origin:	Calcinated phosphate from sewage sludge ash
Valorization method:	Thermochemical process
N:	0.05 %
P:	8.05 %
K:	-
DM content:	79.2 %
Max application rate:	0.6 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on P-content)

Pyrolysis

ID: **CRA**
Waste origin: Sludge from juice-making industry
Valorization method: Hydrothermal conversion (HTC) at 190 °C
N: 6.35 %
P: 0.91 %
K: -
DM content: 29.8 %
Max application rate: 2.7 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID: **MBC**
Waste origin: Chicken manure
Valorization method: Pyrolysis at 300-450 °C
N: 2.94 %
P: 3.06 %
K: -
DM content: 96.5 %
Max application rate: 5.8 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID: **BAG**
Waste origin: Sewage sludge
Valorization method: Pyrolysis at 650 °C
N: 0.76 %
P: 5.23 %
K: -
DM content: 99.0 %
Max application rate: 1.0 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (based on P-content)

Hygienization - Agricultural and food industry waste

ID:	BA1
Waste origin:	Wheat and maize
Valorization method:	Fermentation & distillation
N	5.5 %
P	2.5 %
K	1.5 %
DM content:	87.2 %
Max application rate:	3.1 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID:	MO14
Waste origin:	Vegetable by-products (food industry) & animal proteins
Valorization method:	Pelletising
N:	2%
P:	14%
K:	4 %
DM content:	92.9 %
Max application rate:	8.5 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID:	BIO
Waste origin:	Meat and bones, apatite, vinasse, chicken manure and potassium sulphate (K ₂ SO ₄)
Valorization method:	Pelletising
N:	8 %
P:	4 %
K:	2 %
DM content	93.1 %
Max application rate:	2.1 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID	OPU
Waste origin:	Chicken manure
Valorization method:	Pelletising
N:	2.5 %
P:	2.5 %
K:	-
DM content	83.8 %
Max application rate:	6.8 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

Hygienization - Agricultural and food industry (continued)

ID	FEK
Waste origin:	Chicken manure
Valorization method:	Drying and pressing (extrusion)
N:	4 %
P:	1.3 %
K:	2.4 %
DM content	91.0 %
Max application rate:	4.3 t ha ⁻¹ y ¹ (based on N-content)

ID	OG2
Waste origin:	Horn meal (pig bristles)
Valorization method	Hydrolysis
N:	15 %
P:	0.3 %
K:	0.01 %
DM content:	94.2 %
Max application rate:	1.1 t ha ⁻¹ y ¹ (based on N-content)

ID	ECO
Waste origin:	Blood and feather meal
Valorization method:	Pelletising
N:	13 %
P:	0 %
K:	0 %
DM content:	89.7%
Max application rate:	1.3 t ha ⁻¹ y ¹ (based on N-content)

Hygienization - Sewage sludge

ID	NNP
Waste origin:	Sewage sludge and industrial sludge
Valorization method:	Infrared drying
N:	5.2 %
P:	2.5 %
K:	n.a.
DM content (exp):	90.7%
Max application rate:	3.3 t ha ⁻¹ y ¹ (based on N-content)

ID	RAN
Waste origin:	Sewage sludge and biowaste
Valorization method:	Drying & granulating
N:	3.3 %
P:	3 %
K:	0.25 %
DM content (exp):	84.5 %
Max application rate:	5.2 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID	PRV
Waste origin:	Sewage sludge and biowaste
Valorization method:	Biogasification & hygienisation
N:	3.6 %
P:	2.6 %
K:	0.3 %
DM content (exp):	27.2 %
Max application rate:	4.7 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

Hygienization - Biowaste

ID	PLP
Waste origin:	Biowaste and manure
Valorization method:	Composting
N:	2.01 %
P:	0.34 %
K:	-
DM content (exp):	28.5 %
Max application rate:	8.5 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

ID	VERMI
Waste origin:	Biowaste, peat and wood chips
Valorization method:	Biogasification & vermicomposting
N:	1.3%
P:	-
K:	-
DM content (exp):	28.5 %
Max application rate:	13.1 t ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ (based on N-content)

Summary of BBFs and chemical analyses

Acronym	Valorization method		Waste origin		Country of provenance	Chemical analysis – number of replicates				
	Category	Short description	Category	Short description		7 PCBs (ASE + CC GC/HRMS)	17 PCDDFs (ASE + CC + GC/HRMS)	16 PAHs (ASE + CC + GC/MSMS)	44 PFAS (UAE + SPE + UPLC/QToF)	EOF (UAE + SPE + CIC)
CGO	Crystallisation	Struvite precipitation	Sewage Sludge	Wastewater supernatant	The Netherlands	1	1	1	1	-
EPH	Incineration	>850°C, granulating	Agriculture & food industry	Sunflower husk ash	Ukraine	3	1	3	1	-
PLA	Incineration	>850 °C	Agriculture & food industry	Poultry litter ash	The Netherlands	1	1	1	1	-
ADC	Incineration	900 – 950 °C	Sewage Sludge	Calcined phosphate from sewage sludge ash ³	Germany	1	1	1	1	-
CRA	Pyrolysis	HTC, 190 °C	Agriculture & food industry	Sludge from juice-making industry	Italy	3	1	3	3	3
MBC	Pyrolysis	300-450 °C	Agriculture & food industry	Chicken manure	Switzerland	1	1	1	1	1
BAG	Pyrolysis	650 °C	Sewage sludge	Sewage sludge	Denmark	3	1	3	3	1
BA1	Hygienization	Fermentation & distillation	Agriculture & food industry	Wheat and maize	Austria	1	1	1	1	-
MO14	Hygienization	Pelletising	Agriculture & food industry	Vegetable by-products from food industry & animal proteins	The Netherlands	1	1	1	1	-
BIO	Hygienization	Pelletising	Agriculture & food industry	Meat and bones, apatite, vinasse, chicken manure, K ₂ SO ₄	Finland	1	1	1	3	3
OPU	Hygienization	Pelletising	Agriculture & food industry	Chicken manure	Switzerland	3	1	3	3	3
FEK	Hygienization	Drying and pressing	Agriculture & food industry	Chicken manure	Belgium	1	1	1	3	3
OG2	Hygienization	Hydrolysis	Agriculture & food industry	Horn meal (pig bristles)	Denmark	1	1	1	1	1
ECO	Hygienization	Pelletising	Agriculture & food industry	Blood and feather meal	Finland	1	1	1	3	3
RAN	Hygienization	Drying & granulating	Sewage sludge	Sewage sludge and biowaste	Finland	3	1	3	3	3
PRV	Hygienization	Biogasification & hygienisation	Sewage sludge	Sewage sludge and biowaste	Finland	3	1	3	3	3
NNP	Hygienization	Infrared drying	Sewage sludge	Sewage sludge and industrial sludge	Finland	3	1	3	3	3
VERMI	Hygienization	Biogasification & vermicomposting	Biowaste	Biowaste and manure	Norway	3	1	3	3	1
PLP	Hygienization	Composting	Biowaste	Biowaste, peat and wood chips	Finland	3	1	3	3	1

7 PCBs, 17 PCDDFs, 16 PAHs, 44 PFAS: see the list of target compounds in Si.2 and Si.3. **EOF:** non-target extractable organic fluorine; **ASE:** accelerate solvent extraction (ASE, 180°C, 140 bar, 10 min) with toluene; **CC:** chromatography column, with mixed silica columns (acid, neutral, basic) and aluminium oxide column (for PCBs and PCDDFs) or deactivated silica columns, dimethylformamide clean-up, and aluminium oxide columns (for PAHs); **GC/HRMS:** gas chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry; **GC/MSMS:** gas chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry; **UAE:** ultrasonic assisted extraction (2 x 20 min) with methanol/NH₃; **SPE:** solid phase extraction with Bond Elut Carbon cartridges (100 mg); **UPLC/QToF** = liquid chromatography coupled with quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry; **CIC:** Combustion Ion Chromatography.

2 Additional information on PCBs, PCDD/Fs, and PAHs

7 polychlorinated biphenyls (7 PCBs)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Nb of chlorines	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ d.m.)	13C labeled internal standard	Toxic equivalent factor (TEF)
2,4,4'-Trichlorobiphenyl	7012-37-5	PCB 28	3	0.1	YES	-
2,2',5,5'-Tetrachlorobiphenyl	35693-99-3	PCB 52	4	0.1	YES	-
2,2',4,5,5'-Pentachlorobiphenyl	37680-73-2	PCB 101	5	0.1	YES	-
2,2',3,4,4',5'-Hexachlorobiphenyl	35065-28-2	PCB 138	5	0.1	YES	-
2,2',4,4',5,5'-Hexachlorobiphenyl	35065-27-1	PCB 153	6	0.1	YES	-
2,2',3,4,4',5,5'-Heptachlorobiphenyl	35065-29-3	PCB 180	6	0.1	YES	-
2,3',4,4',5-Pentachlorobiphenyl	31508-00-6	PCB 118	7	0.1	YES	0.0001
17 polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins and dibenzofurans (17 PCDD/Fs)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Nb of chlorines	Limit of quantification (ng kg^{-1} d.m.)	13C labeled internal standard	Toxic equivalent factor (TEF)
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin	1746-01-6	2,3,7,8-TCDD	4	0.05	YES	1
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzodioxin	40321-76-4	1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD	5	0.05	YES	1
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	39227-28-6	1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	57653-85-7	1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzodioxin	19408-74-3	1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzodioxin	35822-46-9	1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	7	0.25	YES	0.01
Octachlorodibenzodioxin	3268-87-9	OCDD	8	0.50	YES	0.003
2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzofuran	51207-31-9	2,3,7,8-TCDF	4	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	57117-41-6	1,2,3,7,8-PeCDF	5	0.05	YES	0.05
2,3,4,7,8-Pentachlorodibenzofuran	57117-31-4	2,3,4,7,8-PeCDF	5	0.05	YES	0.5
1,2,3,4,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	70648-26-9	1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDF	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	57117-44-9	1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDF	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,7,8,9-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	72918-21-9	1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDF	6	0.05	YES	0.1
2,3,4,6,7,8-Hexachlorodibenzofuran	60851-34-5	2,3,4,6,7,8-HxCDF	6	0.05	YES	0.1
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	67562-39-4	1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDF	7	0.15	YES	0.01
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-Heptachlorodibenzofuran	55673-89-7	1,2,3,4,7,8,9-HpCDF	6	0.15	YES	0.01
Octachlorodibenzofuran	39001-02-0	OCDF	8	0.5	YES	0.001
16 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (16 PAHs)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Nb of aromatic rings	Limit of quantification (mg kg^{-1} d.m.)	Deuterated internal standard	Toxic equivalent factor (TEF)
Naphthalene	91-20-3	NAP	2	0.005	YES	0.001
Acenaphthylene	208-96-8	ACY	3	0.001	-	0.001
Acenaphthene	83-32-9	ACE	3	0.001	YES	0.001
Fluorene	86-73-7	FLE	3	0.002	-	0.001
Phenanthrene	5801-8	PHE	3	0.004	YES	0.001
Anthracene	120-12-7	ANT	3	0.001	-	0.01
Fluoranthene	206-44-0	FLU	4	0.001	YES	0.001
Pyrene	129-00-0	PYE	4	0.001	-	0.001
Benz(a)anthracene	56-55-3	BaA	4	0.001	YES	0.1
Chrysene	219-01-9	CRY	4	0.001	-	0.01
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	219-01-9	BbF	5	0.001	-	0.1
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	207-08-9	BkF	5	0.001	-	0.1
Benzo(a)pyrene	50-32-8	BaP	5	0.001	YES	1
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	193-39-5	IDP	6	0.001	-	0.1
Benzo(ghi)perylene	191-24-2	BghiP	6	0.001	-	0.01
Dibenz(ah)anthracene	53-70-3	DBaA	5	0.001	YES	1

3 Additional information on the PFAS quantification method

13 perfluorinated alkyl carboxylic acids (PFCAs)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ d.m.)	mass-labelled internal standard
Perfluorobutanoic acid	375-22-4	PFBA	3	5.0	YES
Perfluoropentanoic acid	422-64-0	PFPA	4	0.5	YES
Perfluorohexanoic acid	307-24-4	PFHxA	5	0.5	YES
Perfluoropentanoic acid	375-85-9	PFHpA	6	0.5	YES
Perfluorooctanoic acid	335-67-1	PFOA	7	0.5	YES
Perfluorononanoic acid	375-95-1	PFNA	8	0.5	YES
Perfluorodecanoic acid	335-76-2	PFDA	9	0.4	YES
Perfluoroundecanoic acid	2058-94-8	PFUnDA	10	0.4	YES
Perfluorododecanoic acid	307-55-1	PFDoDA	11	0.4	YES
Perfluorotridecanoic acid	72629-94-8	PFTrDA	12	0.4	*
Perfluorotetradecanoic acid	376-06-7	PFTeDA	13	0.4	YES
Perfluorooctadecanoic acid	67905-19-5	PFHxDA	15	0.4	*
Perfluorooctadecanoic acid	16517-11-6	PFODA	17	0.4	*
10 perfluorinated alkyl sulphonic acids (PFSA)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ d.m.)	mass-labelled internal standard
Perfluoropropanesulfonic acid	423-41-6	PFPrS	3	0.2	*
perfluorobutane sulphonic acid	375-73-5	PFBS	4	0.1	YES
perfluoropentane sulphonic acid	2706-91-4	PFPeS	5	0.1	*
perfluorohexane sulphonic acid	355-46-4	PFHxS	6	0.1	YES
perfluoroheptane sulphonic acid	375-92-8	PFHpS	7	0.1	*
perfluorooctane sulphonic acids	1763-23-1	PFOS	8	0.05	YES
perfluorodecane sulphonic acids	335-77-3	PFDS	10	0.1	*
Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid	749786-16-1	PFUnDS	11	0.2	*
Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid	79780-39-5	PFDoS	12	0.2	*
Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid	749786-16-1	PFTrDS	13	0.2	*
6 perfluorooctane sulfonamido substances (preFOS)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ d.m.)	mass-labelled internal standard
Perfluorooctanesulfonamide	754-91-6	PFOSA	8	0.1	YES
N-Methyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamide	31506-32-8	N-MeFOSA	8	0.3	*
N-Ethyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamide	4151-50-2	N-EtFOSA	8	0.3	YES
Perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	2806-24-8	FOSAA	8	0.3	*
N-Methyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid	2355-31-9	N-MeFOSAA	8	0.3	*
N-Ethyl-n-perfluorooctanesulfonamidoacetic acid	2991-50-6	N-EtFOSAA	8	0.3	YES
4 fluorotelomer sulfonic acids (FTSA)	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ d.m.)	mass-labelled internal standard
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid	757124-72-4	4:2 FTS	4	0.3	YES
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid	27619-97-2	6:2 FTS	6	0.3	YES
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorodecanesulfonic acid	39108-34-4	8:2 FTS	8	0.3	YES
1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorododecanesulfonic acid	120226-60-0	10:2 FTS	10	0.3	*

3 diPAP	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{d.m.}$)	mass-labelled internal standard
Bis(1H, 1H,2H,2H-Perfluorooctyl) phosphate	407582-79-0	6:2 diPAP	12	0.3	YES
Bis[2-(perfluorooctyl)ethyl] phosphate	678-41-1	8:2 diPAP	16	0.3	YES
bis[2-[N-ethyl(heptadecafluorooctanesulphonyl)amino]ethyl] hydrogen phosphate	2965-52-8	diSamPAP	16	0.3	*
8 other PFAS	CAS Number	Abbreviation	Number of fluorinated carbons	Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{d.m.}$)	mass-labelled internal standard
Perfluoro-p-ethylcyclohexylsulfonic acid	646-83-3	PFECHS	8	0.3	*
Ammonium 4,8-dioxa-3H perfluorononanoate	2250081-67-3	ADONA	6	0.3	*
Perfluoro(2-ethoxyethane)sulphonic acid	113507-82-7	PFEESA	4	0.3	*
2-[(6-chloro-1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-dodecafluorohexyl)oxyl]-1,1,2,2-tetrafluoroethanesulfonic acid	73606-19-6	6:2 F53B	8	0.3	*
2-[(8-chloro-1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8-hexadecafluorohexyl)oxyl]-1,1,2,2-tetrafluoroethanesulfonic acid	83329-89-9	8:2 F53B	10	0.3	*
8Cl-perfluoro-1- octanesulfonate		Cl-PFOS	8	0.3	*
Perfluoro-1-butansulfonamide	30334-69-1	PFBSA	4	0.3	*
Perfluoro-1-hexansulfonamide	41997-13-1	PFHxSA	6	0.3	*

* quantified with a surrogate internal standard (i.e., similar molecular structure)

LC-QToF-HRMS parameters

An Acquity Ultra Performance UPLC system (Waters) was used to inject aliquots of 7 μL extract onto a Waters Acquity BEH C8 reversed phase column (100 x 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm particles. The target compounds were separated at a flow rate of 0.5 mL min^{-1} using acetonitrile (A) and 5.2 mM NH_4OAc in water (B). The following binary gradient was applied: 0 - 1.5 min, 12% of A; 1.5 - 11 min, linear change to 99% of A; 11 - 13 min, 99% of A. The Acquity system was coupled to a Xevo G2-S QToF-HRMS instrument (Waters) using negative ion electrospray ionization (ESI(-)). Mass spectra were registered in full scan mode (mass range m/z of 150-1300. The following optimized parameters were applied: Capillary voltage, 0.7 kV; desolvation temperature, 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; source temperature, 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; nitrogen desolvation gas flow, 800 L h^{-1} . Quantitative analysis was performed employing extracted mass chromatograms from full scan recording using the m/z (typical mass 193 tolerance of 0.03 μ) for the different analytes.

Recoveries

		Fluor. carbon	SewSludge BBF (CRA)	AgriFoodInduWaste-BBF (MO14)	Biowaste-BBF (LIN)	Soil (AUT OPU)	Grains (AUT OPU)	Reference material
PFCAs	PFBA*	3	-	-	-	-	-	1.15
	PFPA	4	0.97	0.92	0.99	1.09	0.75	-
	PFHxA	5	0.76	0.81	0.26	0.95	0.83	-
	PFHpA	6	0.87	0.82	0.95	1.15	0.92	-
	PFOA	7	1.01	0.91	0.72	1.12	0.79	-
	PFNA	8	0.83	0.82	0.99	0.96	0.72	-
	PFDA	9	0.84	1.01	1.05	0.82	0.71	-
	PFUnDA	10	0.84	0.93	0.96	0.91	0.77	-
	PFDoDA	11	0.88	0.82	1.01	0.84	0.71	-
	PFTTrDA	12	0.73	1.05	1.05	0.94	0.73	-
	PFTeDA	13	0.91	0.93	1.11	0.79	1.06	-
	PFHxDA	15	0.86	0.78	0.86	1.12	0.57	-
	PFODA	17	0.68	0.72	0.73	0.81	0.70	-
PFSAs	PFPrS*	3	-	-	-	-	-	1.04
	PFBS	4	0.76	0.75	0.83	0.85	0.75	-
	PFPeS	5	0.86	0.85	0.82	0.82	0.78	-
	PFHxS	6	0.83	0.82	0.79	0.80	0.81	-
	PFHpS	7	0.96	0.99	0.83	0.78	0.81	-
	PFOS	8	0.86	0.86	0.78	0.67	0.73	-
	PFDS	10	0.73	0.71	0.75	0.83	0.77	-
	PFUnDS	11	0.71	0.77	0.80	0.72	0.76	-
	PFDoS	12	0.70	0.78	0.77	0.68	0.73	-
PFTTrDS	13	0.72	0.75	0.71	0.74	0.67	-	
FTSA	4:2 FTS	4	0.82	0.99	0.85	0.77	0.80	-
	6:2 FTS	6	0.87	0.79	0.82	0.73	0.84	-
	8:2 FTS	8	0.96	1.01	0.89	1.07	0.87	-
	10:2 FTS	10	1.08	1.01	1.00	0.82	0.73	-
Pre-FOS	PFOSA	8	1.03	1.11	0.93	0.80	0.85	-
	N-MeFOSA	8	1.09	1.06	0.83	0.75	0.99	-
	N-EtFOSA	8	0.95	0.94	0.85	0.90	0.88	-
	FOSAA	8	0.98	0.94	0.87	0.79	0.92	-
	N-MeFOSAA	8	0.79	0.71	1.01	0.73	0.81	-
	N-EtFOSAA	8	0.92	0.88	1.05	0.87	0.75	-
diPAP	6:2 diPAP	12	0.68	0.70	0.70	0.65	0.67	-
	8:2 diPAP	16	0.58	0.65	0.71	0.61	0.69	-
	diSamPAP	16	0.49	0.67	0.68	0.55	0.47	-
Other PFAS	PFECHS	8	0.98	0.96	0.92	0.90	0.78	-
	ADONA	6	0.93	0.90	0.78	0.90	0.73	-
	PFEESA	4	0.94	0.97	0.94	0.93	0.75	-
	6:2 F53B	8	1.09	0.95	0.98	0.79	0.72	-
	8:2 F53B	10	0.99	0.93	0.96	0.82	0.77	-
	Cl-PFOS	8	0.96	0.94	0.95	0.98	0.91	-
	PFBSA	4	1.04	0.92	0.88	0.90	0.75	-
	PFHxSA	6	0.82	0.80	0.81	1.01	0.85	-
Mean			0.88	0.88	0.87	0.86	0.78	

*PFAS quantified after extraction with acetonitrile

4 Limit values in individual EU countries

Table 1: Limit values for organic contaminants in biosolids (Collivignarelli et al., 2019) (Hall et al., 2020).

	PCBs ($\mu\text{g kg}_{\text{DM}}^{-1}$)	PAHs ($\text{mg kg}_{\text{DM}}^{-1}$)	PCDD/Fs ($\text{ngTEQ kg}_{\text{DM}}^{-1}$)	PFAS ($\mu\text{g kg}_{\text{DM}}^{-1}$)
Germany	100 (for each congener 28, 52, 101, 138, 153 and 180)	1 (for BaP)	100	100 (Sum of PFOS and PFOA, only in some German regions)
France	800 (sum of 7 congeners)	2-5 (<5 for fluoranthene, <2.5 for BbF, <2 for BaP)	-	-
Italy	800	6	25	-
Austria (depending on the regions)	200 – 1'000	6	50-100	-
Sweden	400 (sum of 7 congeners)	3		-
Portugal	800	6	100	-
Denmark	200 (sum of 7 congeners)	3 (sum of ACE, FLE, PHE, FLU, PYR, B(b+j+k)F, B(a)P, IP, BghiP)	-	-
Belgium (depending on the regions)	600-800 (sum of 7 congeners)	3-20	20	-
Luxemburg	200 (sum of 6 congeners)	20 (sum of 16 EPA PAHs)	20	-
Hungary	1'000 (sum of 7 congeners)	10 (sum of 16 EPA PAHs)	-	-
Czech Republic	600 (sum of 7 congeners)	10 (sum ANT, BaA, BbF, BkF, BaP, BghiP, PHE, FLE, CHR, IP, NAP & PYR)	-	-
Romania	800 (sum of 7 congeners)	5 (sum ANT, BaA, BbF, Bjk BkF, BghiP, BaP, CHR, FLE, IP, NAP, PHE & PYR)	-	-
Slovakia	800 (sum of 7 congeners)	6 (sum of ACE, FLU, PHE, FLE, PYR, BbF, Bjk, BkF, BaP, BghiP, IP)	-	-
Croatia	100 (for each congener, 28, 52, 101, 141, 180)		100	-

5 Soil-porewater partition coefficients (K_d) and bioaccumulation factor (BAF)

K_d of PFAS

Soil-porewater partition coefficients (K_d , L kg⁻¹) of PFBS, PFOA and PFOS at pH = 7.2 ± 0.5 reported by Nguyen et al. (2020) in 10 soils of various characteristics:

	PFBA	PFOA	PFOS
S1	0.44	1.04	5.92
S2	0.41	0.68	3.45
S3	0.32	0.81	3.15
S4	0.2	0.64	4.18
S5	0.31	0.74	3.71
S6	0.47	2.84	34.3
S7	0.22	1.42	3.52
S8	0.06	0.53	3.22
S9	0.23	1.18	8.78
S10	0.3	0.86	5.66
Average	0.30	1.07	7.59

Soil	Mesopore (cm ³ /g)	SA (m ² /g)	Silt-plus-Clay (%)	EC (1:5 dS/m)	Boron (Hot water mg/kg)	Ca (cmol ⁺ /kg)	Mg (cmol ⁺ /kg)	Na (cmol ⁺ /kg)	K (cmol ⁺ /kg)	Total C (%)	Total N (%)
S1	0.12	70.40	83	0.30	4.20	25.60	10.70	3.00	2.10	1.20	0.19
S2	0.09	44.22	51	0.20	1.50	5.30	1.40	0.00	0.40	0.63	0.09
S3	0.09	40.72	49	0.06	0.16	2.84	4.32	0.24	0.60	0.07	0.02
S4	0.02	13.13	54	0.60	1.30	2.90	1.50	0.30	0.10	2.64	0.07
S5	0.22	120.67	60	0.20	3.00	21.30	6.30	0.70	1.30	1.40	0.07
S6	0.05	28.93	30	0.25	2.10	20.26	1.14	0.00	0.23	9.18	0.27
S7	0.04	19.60	51	1.30	4.40	3.00	3.30	1.20	0.30	4.47	0.05
S8	0.02	11.39	6	0.07	1.00	1.50	0.64	0.00	0.14	0.75	0.07
S9	0.07	36.42	51	0.15	0.86	14.74	1.40	0.02	1.26	0.99	0.07
S10	0.16	74.84	71	0.03	1.22	11.42	4.00	0.25	0.86	0.20	0.04

Note: Mesopore is cumulative volume of mesopore (2 – 20 nm width), SA is N₂-BET total surface area, EC is electrical conductivity.

BAF of PFAS

Bioaccumulation factors (BAF) for PFBA, PFOA and PFOS in cereal grains were reported by Doucette et al. (2018), Krippner et al. (2014), Stahl et al. (2009) and Wen et al. (2014):

	Maize grains (Krippner et al. 2015)	Oat grains (Stahl et al. 2009)	Wheat grains (Stahl et al 2009)	Wheat grains (Wen et al. 2014)
PFBA	0.133 – 0.229	-	0.48	0.43
PFOA	0.002	0.048 – 0.054	0.111	0.16
PFOS	-	0.004 – 0.017	0.062	0.054

K_d PAHs, PCBs and PCDD/Fs:

Soil-porewater partition coefficients (K_d , L kg⁻¹) for PCBs, PAHs and PCDD/Fs were calculated from K_{oc} ($\log K_{oc} = 0.00028 + (0.983 \times \log K_{ow})$) (Di Toro, 1985) at an organic carbon content (f_{oc}) of 3 % ($K_d = K_{oc} \times f_{oc}$):

	ACE	ACY	FLE	PHE	ANT	FLU	PYE	BaA	CHR	BaP	BbF	BkF	BghiP	DBahA	IDP
log K _{ow}	3.92	3.94	4.18	4.46	4.45	5.16	4.88	5.76	5.81	6.13	5.78	6.11	6.63	6.54	6.7
log K _{oc}	3.85	3.87	4.11	4.38	4.37	5.07	4.80	5.66	5.71	6.03	5.68	6.01	6.52	6.43	6.59
K _d	214	224	386	727	711	3546	1881	13787	15439	31856	14426	30446	98785	80579	115745

	PCB 28	PCB 52	PCB 101	PCB 118	PCB 138	PCB 153	PCB 180
log Kow	5.67	5.84	6.38	6.74	6.83	6.92	7.36
log Koc	5.57	5.74	6.27	6.63	6.71	6.80	7.24
Kd	11246	16524	56097	126713	155343	190441	515562

	2,3,7,8-TCDD	1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD	1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	OCDD	2,3,7,8-TCDF	1,2,3,7,8-PeCDF	1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDF	1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDF	OCDF
log Kow	6.1	6.2	6.85	8	8.2	5.6	6.19	7	7.4	8
log Koc	6.00	6.09	6.73	7.86	8.06	5.51	6.09	6.88	7.27	7.86
Kd	29765	37325	162537	2194832	3451447	9598	36490	228245	564419	2194832

BAF of PAHs, PCBs, and PCDD/Fs

BAF for PAHs, PCBs and PCDD/Fs in cereal shoots were reported by (Kacálková and Tlustoš, 2011; Lorenzi et al., 2016; Paraíba et al., 2010; Strek et al., 1981). They are very low (< 1) because of the high sorption to soil matter (high K_d). PCDD/Fs and PCBs have often not been detected in cereal grains (Hundal et al., 2008; Webber et al., 1994). The main uptake for these compounds being from the atmosphere rather than the soil (Nizzetto et al., 2008; Su et al., 2007). Note that for plants BAF and bioaccumulation factor (BCF) are used interchangeably in the literature (Lesmeister et al., 2021).

	Maize shoot Strek et al, 1981	Maize leaves or aboveground mass (Kacálková and Tlustoš, 2011)	Maize grain* (Paraíba et al., 2010)	Maize kernels (Lorenzi et al., 2016)
PAHs		0.03 – 1	0.004-0.65 (NAP not incl.) 1.37 (NAP)	
PCBs	0.001	< 0.005		0.0017
PCDD/FS				0.0003

* BCF expressed in $C_{\text{plant}}/C_{\text{water}}$ were converted in $C_{\text{plant}}/C_{\text{soil}}$ by using C_w and K_d

6 Additional information on field trial sites

Field site location and climate data (1991-2021) <http://www.climate-data.org>.

Site	Country	Coordinates Latitude / longitude	Climate station	Climate zone (Köppen)	Mean annual temperature °C	Annual precipitation mm
LUKE	Finland	60.8638 / 23.5212	Jokioinen	Dfb	5.3	724
BOKU	Austria	48.3211 / 16.1018	Langenlebarndorf	Cfb	10.4	759

Basic soil characteristics at the two field sites. Soil samples were taken from the plough layer, i.e. 0-25cm for Finland; 0-30 cm for Austria. Soil type classification according to WRB. SOC = soil organic carbon.

Site	Soil type	Clay %	Silt %	Sand %	SOC g kg ⁻¹	pH _{H2O} -	pH _{CaCl2} -	CaCO ₃ g kg ⁻¹	Olsen P mg kg ⁻¹
BOKU	Chernozem	44	39	17	20.0	6.9	6.2	-	3.4
LUKE	Luvic Stagnosol	60	22	18	31.2	6.2	-	-	9.5

Jokioinen, Finland

Soil type of the experimental field is Luvic Stagnosol. Experimental field had been under natural grass since 1990's and no farming practices were conducted on the field until autumn 2019 when glyphosate treatment were given to remove grass stand. After two months (November 2019) field was ploughed. Spring barley was grown in summer 2020 and only N fertilization as calcium ammonium nitrate was given. Field was again sprayed with glyphosate in autumn 2020 and ploughed end of October 2020. Prior to planting in spring 2021, topsoil (up to 10 cm) was harrowed, potassium sulphate spread across the experimental area to provide potassium 50 kg ha⁻¹ and BBFs (30 kg P ha⁻¹) were spread on the dedicated plots (5 m * 10 m), mixed to a depth of 0-6 cm with a rotary tiller and barley was sown. After harvest (3 m * 8 m) in the beginning of September, soil samples were taken from depth of 0-5 cm. Each soil sample consisted of ten subsamples from each plot. Drought during the growing season of 2021 restricted barley growth and yields were less than during the two following years. Figure below shows the experimental field just before harvest.

Langenlebarn, Austria

Soil type of the experimental field is a chernozem. The parcel belongs to a farmer who does conventional agriculture. Besides the BBF, the parcel was fertilized with 220 kg ha⁻¹ Alzon and 500 kg ha⁻¹ potassium oxide (K₂O). Plots were of 6 x 9 m. BBFs were applied manually and mixed in with the soil using a rack. The plant grown was maize (Pioneer P8307 Reifezahl 250). The grains come from inner rows of each parcel to avoid contamination between treatments. Fertilizers were applied, after ploughing, at the end of April 2021, and the seedbed preparation was done with harrow. Harvest was conducted in October 2021.

7 Contaminant concentrations in BBFs

	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)												
PCBs	CGO	EPH_1	EPH_2	EPH_3	PLA	ADC	CRA_1	CRA_2	CRA_3	MBC	BAG_1	BAG_2	BAG_3
PCB 28	< 0,10	2.7	3.1	3.0	0.29	< 0,10	0.48	0.41	0.45	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 52	< 0,10	0.96	1.04	1.01	0.16	< 0,10	0.52	0.46	0.49	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 101	< 0,10	0.18	0.22	0.19	< 0,10	< 0,10	0.47	0.42	0.45	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 138	< 0,10	< 0,10	0.11	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	0.54	0.49	0.51	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 153	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	1.53	1.46	1.48	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 180	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	3.19	2.83	2.96	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
PCB 118	< 0,10	0.15	0.12	0.13	< 0,10	< 0,10	0.40	0.34	0.38	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10	< 0,10
	Concentrations (ng TEQ kg^{-1})												
PCDD/Fs	CGO	EPH_1	EPH_2	EPH_3	PLA	ADC	CRA_1	CRA_2	CRA_3	MBC	BAG_1	BAG_2	BAG_3
2,3,7,8-TCDD	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	0.08	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	0.11	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	< 0,25	< 0,25	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,25	< 0,25	5.77	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,25	0.37	n.a.	n.a.
OCDD	< 0,50	0.95	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,50	< 0,50	19.3	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,50	0.63	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,7,8-TCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.55	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8-PeCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.38	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,4,7,8-PeCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	0.08	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.49	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	0.10	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.61	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.54	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,4,6,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	< 0,05	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	0.65	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDF	< 0,15	< 0,15	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,15	< 0,15	0.72	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,15	2.93	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-HpCDF	< 0,15	< 0,15	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,15	< 0,15	< 0,15	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,15	< 0,15	n.a.	n.a.
OCDF	< 0,50	< 0,50	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,50	< 0,50	1.84	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,50	0.55	n.a.	n.a.
	Concentrations (mg kg^{-1})												
PAHs	CGO	EPH_1	EPH_2	EPH_3	PLA	ADC	CRA_1	CRA_2	CRA_3	MBC	BAG_1	BAG_2	BAG_3
NAP	0.008	0.018	0.024	0.022	0.009	0.011	0.105	0.089	0.096	0.413	14.7	15.9	16.9
ACY	< 0,001	< 0,004	< 0,003	0.004	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.005	0.007	0.005	0.001	0.491	0.533	0.561
ACE	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,002	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.017	0.014	0.016	0.006	0.017	0.02	0.022
FLE	< 0,003	0.012	0.011	0.015	< 0,002	< 0,003	0.005	0.007	0.006	0.097	0.007	0.009	0.01
PHE	< 0,004	0.078	0.082	0.085	< 0,005	< 0,004	0.067	0.056	0.061	0.137	3.94	4.27	4.35
ANT	< 0,001	0.009	0.011	0.012	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.011	0.009	0.0	0.016	0.686	0.725	0.738
FLU	0.004	0.038	0.039	0.043	< 0,003	< 0,001	0.030	0.025	0.026	0.034	0.738	0.774	0.792
PYE	0.004	0.041	0.043	0.047	< 0,003	< 0,001	0.049	0.040	0.043	0.035	0.732	0.813	0.845
BaA	< 0,001	0.014	0.012	0.012	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.016	0.089	0.099	0.105
CRY	< 0,002	0.013	0.015	0.016	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.008	0.006	0.007	0.033	0.111	0.120	0.126
BbF	0.003	0.017	0.021	0.018	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,005	0.004	< 0,004	0.009	0.024	0.026	0.028
BkF	< 0,001	0.007	0.007	0.008	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,002	< 0,002	< 0,002	0.002	0.011	0.013	0.014
BaP	< 0,001	0.019	0.022	0.023	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.011	0.022	0.025	0.025
IDP	< 0,001	0.031	0.033	0.027	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.003	0.002	0.003	0.006	0.005	0.007	0.006
BghiP	< 0,001	0.043	0.047	0.047	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.005	0.005	0.008	0.007
DBaHA	< 0,001	0.005	0.006	0.004	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,001	< 0,001	0.002	0.002	0.003	0.003

	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)														
PCBs	PLP_1	PLP_2	PLP_3	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	RAN_1	RAN_2	RAN_3	PRV_1	PRV_2	PRV_3	NNP_1	NNP_2	NNP_3
PCB 28	4.27	4.39	4.31	0.68	0.77	0.79	0.87	1.03	0.91	0.82	0.93	0.89	0.62	0.64	0.65
PCB 52	2.72	2.55	2.65	0.87	0.97	1.07	0.91	0.98	0.95	0.72	0.80	0.82	0.57	0.61	0.58
PCB 101	1.75	2.01	1.94	0.98	1.06	1.1	1.02	1.04	1.01	0.71	0.81	0.79	0.71	0.81	0.76
PCB 138	1.54	1.79	1.69	1.28	1.49	1.47	1.33	1.35	1.32	0.71	0.85	0.82	1.12	1.30	1.16
PCB 153	1.60	1.88	1.80	1.77	2.00	1.97	1.84	1.98	1.87	0.95	1.09	1.03	1.64	1.83	1.70
PCB 180	0.92	1.06	1.05	0.78	0.89	0.92	1.16	1.09	1.12	0.52	0.62	0.54	1.16	1.25	1.18
PCB 118	1.41	1.47	1.51	0.85	0.93	0.95	0.53	0.52	0.49	0.36	0.43	0.40	0.48	0.42	0.45
	Concentrations (ng TEQ kg^{-1})														
PCDD/Fs	PLP_1	PLP_2	PLP_3	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	RAN_1	RAN_2	RAN_3	PRV_1	PRV_2	PRV_3	NNP_1	NNP_2	NNP_3
2,3,7,8-TCDD	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	0.14	n.a.	n.a.	0.14	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	0.09	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8-PeCDD	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	0.49	n.a.	n.a.	0.42	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,10	n.a.	n.a.	0.85	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDD	0.11	n.a.	n.a.	0.69	n.a.	n.a.	0.44	n.a.	n.a.	0.30	n.a.	n.a.	0.72	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDD	1.21	n.a.	n.a.	1.46	n.a.	n.a.	3.02	n.a.	n.a.	0.68	n.a.	n.a.	3.76	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDD	0.41	n.a.	n.a.	0.9	n.a.	n.a.	1.41	n.a.	n.a.	0.42	n.a.	n.a.	2.18	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDD	27.8	n.a.	n.a.	31.3	n.a.	n.a.	41.9	n.a.	n.a.	10.7	n.a.	n.a.	92.6	n.a.	n.a.
OCDD	182	n.a.	n.a.	203	n.a.	n.a.	333	n.a.	n.a.	88.5	n.a.	n.a.	704	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,7,8-TCDF	< 0,10	n.a.	n.a.	1.65	n.a.	n.a.	1.45	n.a.	n.a.	0.32	n.a.	n.a.	0.61	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8-PeCDF	< 0,07	n.a.	n.a.	0.81	n.a.	n.a.	0.94	n.a.	n.a.	0.28	n.a.	n.a.	0.5	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,4,7,8-PeCDF	< 0,07	n.a.	n.a.	1.55	n.a.	n.a.	1.32	n.a.	n.a.	0.26	n.a.	n.a.	1.08	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,07	n.a.	n.a.	1.09	n.a.	n.a.	2.45	n.a.	n.a.	0.38	n.a.	n.a.	1.17	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,6,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	1.27	n.a.	n.a.	1.33	n.a.	n.a.	0.47	n.a.	n.a.	1.20	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,7,8,9-HxCDF	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	0.07	n.a.	n.a.	0.14	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,05	n.a.	n.a.	< 0,07	n.a.	n.a.
2,3,4,6,7,8-HxCDF	< 0,07	n.a.	n.a.	1.30	n.a.	n.a.	1.18	n.a.	n.a.	0.21	n.a.	n.a.	1.38	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,6,7,8-HpCDF	6.84	n.a.	n.a.	5.3	n.a.	n.a.	30.2	n.a.	n.a.	16.1	n.a.	n.a.	18.0	n.a.	n.a.
1,2,3,4,7,8,9-HpCDF	< 0,15	n.a.	n.a.	0.33	n.a.	n.a.	1.01	n.a.	n.a.	0.25	n.a.	n.a.	0.83	n.a.	n.a.
OCDF	5.92	n.a.	n.a.	5.62	n.a.	n.a.	20.6	n.a.	n.a.	25.2	n.a.	n.a.	27.6	n.a.	n.a.
	Concentrations (mg kg^{-1})														
PAHs	PLP_1	PLP_2	PLP_3	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	RAN_1	RAN_2	RAN_3	PRV_1	PRV_2	PRV_3	NNP_1	NNP_2	NNP_3
NAP	0.114	0.129	0.121	0.054	0.122	0.104	0.268	0.288	0.33	0.015	0.018	0.021	0.054	0.060	0.063
ACY	0.011	0.013	0.013	0.008	0.015	0.014	0.053	0.064	0.061	0.005	0.007	0.008	0.006	0.008	0.007
ACE	0.014	0.018	0.015	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.013	0.010	0.013	0.004	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.010	0.007
FLE	0.039	0.043	0.042	0.011	0.020	0.022	0.067	0.079	0.077	0.011	0.013	0.013	0.019	0.022	0.020
PHE	0.188	0.206	0.194	0.097	0.185	0.183	0.591	0.571	0.628	0.046	0.049	0.052	0.088	0.097	0.095
ANT	0.031	0.027	0.033	0.016	0.039	0.039	0.134	0.128	0.121	0.013	0.015	0.017	0.013	0.014	0.016
FLU	0.086	0.086	0.089	0.082	0.190	0.219	0.609	0.591	0.662	0.032	0.030	0.035	0.107	0.119	0.123
PYE	0.096	0.101	0.103	0.078	0.175	0.182	0.587	0.613	0.637	0.039	0.044	0.047	0.142	0.146	0.149
BaA	0.016	0.019	0.018	0.020	0.058	0.091	0.109	0.104	0.129	0.010	0.012	0.013	0.05	0.056	0.052
CRY	0.030	0.027	0.032	0.037	0.093	0.122	0.137	0.127	0.152	0.014	0.015	0.017	0.062	0.059	0.058
BbF	0.018	0.020	0.022	0.022	0.062	0.085	0.104	0.100	0.109	0.009	0.012	0.011	0.006	0.067	0.063
BkF	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.011	0.036	0.051	0.058	0.053	0.049	0.006	0.008	0.006	0.039	0.043	0.043
BaP	0.011	0.013	0.012	0.014	0.040	0.058	0.074	0.069	0.072	0.007	0.010	0.011	0.048	0.055	0.052
IDP	0.011	0.013	0.013	0.019	0.048	0.055	0.073	0.066	0.065	0.006	0.008	0.008	0.08	0.082	0.084
BghiP	0.030	0.034	0.031	0.020	0.047	0.056	0.11	0.119	0.111	0.008	0.010	0.012	0.092	0.085	0.090
DBahA	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.01	0.014	0.016	0.015	0.013	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.018	0.016	0.018

PFAS	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)										
	CGO	EPH	PLA	ADC	CRA_1	CRA_2	CRA_3	MBC	BAG_1	BAG_2	BAG_3
PFBA*	< 5	< 5	< 5	< 5	5.9	6.1	6.2	5.1	< 5	< 5	< 5
PFPA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHxA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHpA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFOA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFNA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFUnDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFDoDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFTTrDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFTeDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFHxDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFODA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFPrS*	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	< 0.2	0.51
PFBS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFPeS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHxS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHpS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFOS	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	0.17	0.21	0.15	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
PFDS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFUnDS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFDoS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFTTrDS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFOSA	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
N-MeFOSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
FOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-MeFOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
4:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
10:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 diPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 diPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
diSamPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFECHS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
ADONA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFEESA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 F53B	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 F53B	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
Cl-PFOS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFBSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFHxSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3

*PFBA and PFPrS were extracted with acetonitrile, (not with a MeOH/NH3 solution) as explained in section 2.4 of the manuscript.

PFAS	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)										
	BA1	MO14	BIO_1	BIO_2	BIO_2	OPU_1	OPU_2	OPU_3	FEK_1	FEK_2	FEK_3
PFBA*	<5	<5	<5	6.2	5.9	8.2	6.7	5.3	<5	<5	5.2
PFPA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHxA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHpA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFOA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFNA	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFUnDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFDoDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFTTrDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFTeDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFHxDA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFODA	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFPrS*	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFBS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFPeS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHxS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHpS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFOS	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05	0.11	0.09	0.11
PFDS	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFUnDS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFDoS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFTTrDS	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFOSA	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
N-MeFOSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
FOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-MeFOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSAA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
4:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
10:2 FTS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 diPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 diPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
diSamPAP	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFECHS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
ADONA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFEESA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 F53B	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 F53B	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
Cl-PFOS	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFBSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFHxSA	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3

*PFBA and PFPrS were extracted with acetonitrile, (not with a MeOH/NH3 solution) as explained in section 2.4 of the manuscript.

PFAS	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)								
	OG2_1	OG2_2	OG2_3	ECO_1	ECO_2	ECO_3	BL_1	BL_2	BL_3
PFBA*	<5	5.3	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5	<5
PFPA	n.a.	<0,5	n.a.	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHxA	n.a.	<0,5	n.a.	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFHpA	n.a.	<0,5	n.a.	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFOA	n.a.	<0,5	n.a.	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFNA	n.a.	<0,5	n.a.	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
PFDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFUnDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFDoDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4
PFTTrDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,5	<0,4
PFTeDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,6	<0,4
PFHxDA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,7	<0,4
PFODA	n.a.	<0,4	n.a.	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,4	<0,8	<0,4
PFPrS*	n.a.	<0,2	n.a.	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFBS	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFPeS	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHxS	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFHpS	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFOS	n.a.	0.05	n.a.	0.08	0.06	0.06	<0,05	<0,05	<0,05
PFDS	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
PFUnDS	n.a.	<0,2	n.a.	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFDoS	n.a.	<0,2	n.a.	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFTTrDS	n.a.	<0,2	n.a.	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2	<0,2
PFOSA	n.a.	<0,1	n.a.	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
N-MeFOSA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
FOSAA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-MeFOSAA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
N-EtFOSAA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
4:2 FTS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 FTS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 FTS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
10:2 FTS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 diPAP	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 diPAP	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
diSamPAP	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFECHS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
ADONA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFEESA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
6:2 F53B	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
8:2 F53B	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
Cl-PFOS	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFBSA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3
PFHxSA	n.a.	<0,3	n.a.	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3	<0,3

*PFBA and PFPrS were extracted with acetonitrile, (not with a MeOH/NH3 solution) as explained in section 2.4 of the manuscript.

PFAS	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)														
	PLP_1	PLP_2	PLP_3	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	VERMI_1	RAN_1	RAN_2	RAN_3	PRV_1	PRV_2	PRV_3	NNP_1	NNP_2	NNP_3
PFBA*	8.3	6.1	5.6	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFPA	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFHxA	1.21	1.32	1.14	1.89	1.99	2.03	1.41	1.44	1.35	4.47	5.41	3.92	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFHpA	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFOA	0.74	0.77	0.65	0.68	0.86	0.85	0.59	0.53	0.53	1.83	2.35	1.71	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFNA	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0.57	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5
PFDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	0.79	0.73	0.71	1.22	1.54	1.15	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFUnDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFDoDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFTTrDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFTeDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFHxDA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFODA	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4	<0.4
PFPrS*	0.47	0.31	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	0.21	0.22	0.21	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
PFBS	0.19	0.23	0.21	0.42	0.49	0.47	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.18	0.23	0.17	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
PFPeS	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.12	0.13	0.11	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
PFHxS	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.12	0.13	0.11	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
PFHpS	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
PFOS	0.64	0.74	0.6	0.44	0.49	0.46	3.76	3.66	3.65	11.91	14.67	10.78	0.82	0.77	0.74
PFDS	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
PFUnDS	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
PFDoS	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
PFTTrDS	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
PFOSA	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.15	0.16	0.14	0.19	0.28	0.18	0.13	0.12	0.15
N-MeFOSA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
N-EtFOSA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
FOSAA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
N-MeFOSAA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	1.77	0.56	1.79	2.06	1.52	1.28	1.27	1.46	0.59
N-EtFOSAA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	1.94	1.29	1.51	2.34	2.86	1.94	1.79	1.61	1.59
4:2 FTS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
6:2 FTS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	0.79	0.85	0.77	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
8:2 FTS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	0.47	0.43	0.46
10:2 FTS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	0.45	0.41	0.39	1.35	1.49	1.15	1.19	1.18	1.12
6:2 diPAP	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
8:2 diPAP	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
diSamPAP	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
PFECHS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
ADONA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
PFEESA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
6:2 F53B	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
8:2 F53B	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
Cl-PFOS	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
PFBSA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3
PFHxSA	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3	<0.3

*PFBA and PFPrS were extracted with acetonitrile, (not with a MeOH/NH₃ solution) as explained in section 2.4 of the manuscript.

8 Impact of waste origins and valorization methods

	AgriFoodInduWaste BBF	Biowaste BBF	SewSludge BBF	Results of statistical test
$\Sigma 45\text{PFAS}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	2.8 ± 2.8	6.7 ± 3.5	15.2 ± 10.8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant differences among the means: ANOVA, $F(2,9) = 5.99$, $p < 0.01$ ANOVA residuals normally distributed: Shapiro-Wilk: $W = 0.92$, $p = 0.07$ SewSludge-BBFs > AgriFoodInduWaste BBFs: Tukey, $p < 0.01$ No significant difference for Biowaste-BBFs Tukey, $p > 0.05$
$\Sigma 7\text{PCBs}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	0.11 ± 0.18	11.3 ± 3.8	6.5 ± 1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant differences among the means: ANOVA, $F(2,19) = 47.2$, $p < 0.01$ ANOVA residuals normally distributed: Shapiro-Wilk: $W = 0.94$, $p = 0.23$ SewSludge-BBFs > AgriFoodInduWaste BBFs: Tukey test, $p < 0.01$ Biowaste-BBFs > SewSludge-BBFs: Tukey test, $p < 0.01$ Biowaste-BBFs > AgriFoodInduWaste BBFs: Tukey test, $p < 0.01$
$\Sigma 17\text{PCDD/Fs}$ (ng TEQ kg^{-1})	0.24 ± 0.62	1.48 ± 1.29	2.45 ± 1.59	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant differences among the means: ANOVA, $F(2,9) = 5.43$, $p = 0.028$ ANOVA residuals normally distributed: Shapiro-Wilk: $W = 0.91$, $p = 0.19$ SewSludge-BBFs > AgriFoodInduWaste BBFs: Tukey, $p = 0.026$ No significant difference for Biowaste-BBFs Tukey, $p > 0.05$
$\Sigma 16\text{PAHs}$ (mg kg^{-1})	0.26 ± 0.36	0.86 ± 0.30	1.41 ± 1.28	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant differences among the means: ANOVA ($F(2,19) = 4.27$, $p = 0.03$ ANOVA residuals not fully normally distributed*: Shapiro-Wilk: $W = 0.89$, $p = 0.015$ SewSludge-BBFs > AgriFoodInduWaste BBFs: Tukey, $p = 0.023$ No significant difference for Biowaste-BBFs Tukey, $p > 0.05$
EOF ($\mu\text{g F kg}^{-1}$)	147 ± 176	48 ± 7	320 ± 133	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANOVA, $F(2,21) = 4.34$, $p = 0.027$ Tukey, $p = 0,047$ ANOVA residuals not fully normally distributed*: Shapiro-Wilk: $W = 0.84$, $p = 0.002$ No significant difference for Biowaste-BBFs Tukey, $p > 0.05$

*Data in some groups are however normally distributed, and ANOVA can tolerate data that is non-normal with only a small effect on the Type I error rate.

9 PFOS concentrations reported in literature

Comment about the sample year: Individual sample years were used when PFOS concentrations were reported annually. An average value was used for studies mentioning sampling campaigns conducted over a range of years without providing PFOS concentrations for individual years, e.g., “2013” was used for the results from Stahl et al., (2018) who mentioned that “A total of 201 samples of sewage sludge and 45 samples of biowaste were collected from 2010 to 2016”.

Comment about the mean and median concentrations: When mean and/or median concentrations were not directly reported in the studies, they were calculated from individual PFOS concentrations (when available). The absence of median values in the table indicates that only the mean values were provided (no median values, nor individual values to determine them).

Comment about the presence of local PFAS source: The data represent diffusely polluted municipal sewage sludge that – to the best of our knowledge - were not affected by major PFAS hotspots. Potential minor local PFAS sources reported by some of these studies are mentioned in the table below.

EUROPE

Study	Sample year	Median ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Number of WWTPs (and country) Potential local PFAS sources
Bossi et al. (2008)	2004	-	18.4	Six WWTPs (Denmark)
Becker et al. (2008)	2006	100	100	One WWTP (Germany) 2/3 of wastewater came from commercial and industrial sources including breweries, food, plastics and tobacco industries.
Zhang et al. (2010)	2008	213	333	Three WWTPs (Switzerland)
Navarro et al. (2011)	2006	28.3	63.9	Twenty WWTPs (Spain)
Llorca et al. (2011)	2010	73.5	84.2	One WWTP (Spain)
Esparza et al. (2011)	2009	39.5	40.5	Four WWTPs (The Netherlands)
Sun et al. (2011)	2008	78.0	139	Twenty WWTPs (Switzerland) The sewage sludges from three WWTPs presented PFOS levels ca. 8x higher than sewage sludges from the 17 other WWTPs. These three WWTPs were probably impacted by local wastewater sources (incl. chromium electroplating and surface finishing industries).
Gómez-Canela et al. (2012)	2012	1.91	1.94	Fifteen WWTPs (Spain (12) and Germany (3)) The three (Spanish) sewage sludges presenting the highest PFOS concentrations were produced by WWTPs treating wastewater from industrial sectors (with vehicle, textile, and chemical industries).
Arvaniti et al. (2012)	2009	4.3	4.3	Two WWTPs (Greece). One received 80% domestic wastewater and 20% industrial wastewater, the other only domestic wastewater.
Stasinakis et al. (2013)	2011	6.5	7.3	One WWTP (Greece)
Martínez-Moral and Tena (2013)	2013	1.38	1.32	Different WWTPs (Spain)
Perkola and Sainio (2013)	2010	63.0	63.0	One WWTP (Finland)
Campo et al. (2014)	2010	51.7	229.1	Sixteen WWTPs 16 (Spain)
	2011	0.01	38.0	
Filipovic and Berger (2015)	2013	2.9	4.2	Three WWTPs (Sweden)
Alder and van der Voet (2015)	2011	75	177.1	PFAS-related industrial and commercial activities in the catchment of 35 of the 45 WWTPs: metal plating industries (22), fire brigade training sites and foam suppliers (8), textile/textile finishing industries (9), landfill leachates (5), paper manufactures (5), packaging supplier (1), airports (2).
Ulrich et al. (2016)	2008	-	48.0	Several WWTPs (Germany)
	2009	-	21.5	
	2010	-	18.0	
	2011	-	23.0	
	2012	-	24.0	
2013	-	15.5		
Navarro et al. (2016)	2011	8.2	14.8	Sixteen WWTPs (Spain)
Zacs and Bartkevics (2016)	2015	0.16	0.27	WWTPs from the Baltic area
Eriksson et al. (2017)	2012	4.7	5.2	Three WWTPs (Sweden).
	2014	2.7	3.2	The three WWTPs received domestic wastewater and water from hospitals. One WWTP received wastewater from textile and chemical industries.
	2015	3.0	2.4	
Stahl et al. (2018)	2013	7.3	23.1	Different sewage treatment plants (Gemrnay)
Abril et al. (2020)	2018	20.1	20.4	Ten sewage treatment plants (Spain)
Aro et al. (2021)	2017	3.9	4.9	Ten WWTPs (Finland, Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Faroe Islands)
Fredriksson et al. (2022)	2004	27.5	27.5	Two WWTPs (Sweden)
	2005	30.0	30.0	
	2007	26.0	26.0	
	2008	27.5	27.5	
	2009	27.5	27.5	
	2010	20.0	20.0	
	2011	15.0	15.0	
	2012	19.8	19.8	
	2013	10.1	10.1	
	2014	13.0	13.0	
2015	12.0	12.0		
2016	6.7	6.7		
Sørmo et al. (2023)	2021	24.5	25.0	Three WWTPs (Norway)

AMERICA

Study	Sample year	Median ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Mean ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Number of WWTPs (and country) Potential local PFAS sources
Higgins et al. (2005)	2001	77.3	400	Eight WWTPs (USA). All the WWTP received at least 50% domestic waste. One WWTP received papermill effluent; it however presented some of the lowest PFOS concentrations.
Schultz et al. (2006)	2004	-	100	One WWTP (USA)
Sinclair and Kannan (2006)	2004	30	31	Two WWTPs (USA) One WWTP influenced by domestic and commercial discharge, the other WWTP had an additional industrial discharge. Only small difference in PFOS concentrations between sludges (mean: 37 vs. 25 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, median: 28 vs. 32 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Loganathan et al. (2007)	2005	61.0	61.7	Two WWTPs (USA).
D'eon et al. (2009)	2002	41.0	95.2	Six WWTPs (Canada)
Sepulvado et al. (2011)	2005	145	143	Biosolids (USA). No information about WWTPs (biosolids obtained from Metropolitan Water Reclamation District of Greater Chicago)
Venkatesan and Halden (2013)	2001	-	403	Ninety-four WWTPs (USA)
Guerra et al. (2014)	2010	13	534* or 29.6	Fifteen WWTPs (Canada). Sludges from one WWTP receiving industrial wastewater contained very high PFOS concentrations (13'100 and 2099 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). These concentrations impact very much the mean value: 534.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (considered) vs. 29.6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (not considered)
Armstrong et al. (2016)	2005	1.0	1.1	One WWTP (USA)
	2006	50.4	51.7	
	2007	28.8	27.3	
	2008	21.1	21.3	
	2009	19.0	19.3	
	2010	18.8	15.6	
	2011	13.5	15.6	
	2012	12.6	12.1	
2013	17.0	21.2		
Gottschall et al. (2017)	2008	7.2	7.2	One WWTP (Canada) The WWTP processed domestic, commercial and industrial wastewater
Kim Lazcano et al. (2019)	2018	9.9	10.1	Four WWTPs (USA). PFOS concentrations in sludges prior studied treatment process have been used to determine the mean and median values.
Letcher et al. (2020)	2017	5.7	10.9	Twenty WWTPs (Canada)
Kim Lazcano et al. (2020)	2014	10.3	18.2	Eleven commercially available bio-based products (USA)
Gewurtz et al. (2024)	2009	22.8	1072* or 45.8	Twenty-seven WWTPs (Canada) Sludges from one WWTP presented high PFOS concentrations in 2009 (7617.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$); no significant industrial source was known. These concentrations impact very much the mean value: 1072 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (considered) vs. 45.8 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (not considered)
	2010	8.3	10.5	
	2011	14.6	12.8	
	2013	14.7	37.7	
	2014	3.54	62.3	
	2015	6.0	8.4	
	2016	9.4	11.0	
	2018	12.1	15.6	
	2019	9.9	17.7	
	2021	7.9	10.3	

* Value not considered in the determination of the temporal trend (Figure 4) because the contribution of a local hotspot was suspected.

Median values

Mean values

10 PCB, PCDD/F, and PAH concentrations reported in literature

PCBs

Study	Sample year	Mean ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
(Alcock and Jones, 1993)	1993	292
(McGrath et al., 2000)	1992	67
(Eljarrat et al., 2003)	2000	40.3
(Stevens et al., 2003)	2000	80.1
(Katsoyiannis and Samara, 2004; Ma and Shih, 2010)	2002	550
(Blanchard et al., 2004)	1999	617
(Abad et al., 2005)	2002	48
(Zennegg et al., 2013)	1993	235
	2002	169
	2007	97
	2012	68
(Fijalkowski et al., 2017)	1990	2000
	1996	200
	2001	90
	2012	50
(Roskosch and Heidecke, 2018)	2006	91
(Kaya et al., 2015)	2012	30
(Sørmo et al., 2024)	2021	11.6
(Sava et al., 2024)	2023	6.3

PCDD/Fs

Study	Sample year	Mean (ng TEQ kg ⁻¹)
(Zennegg et al., 2013)	1993	19.7
	2002	19.6
	2007	10.2
	2012	7.6
(Abad et al., 2005)	2002	38
(Roskosch and Heidecke, 2018)	2006	14
(Fijalkowski et al., 2017)	1990	62
	1996	25
	2001	14
	2012	5.4
(Eljarrat et al., 2003)	2000	9.3
(Sørmo et al., 2024)	2021	4.4
(Stevens et al., 2001)	2000	64.7
(Fuentes et al., 2007)	2003	24.6
(Martínez et al., 2007)	2004	20.3
(Eljarrat et al., 1999)	1996	55
	1983	620
(Elskens et al., 2013)	2011	3.0

PAHs

Study	Sample year	Mean (mg μg^{-1})	Median (mg μg^{-1})
(Berset and Holzer, 1999)	1998	7.1	6.7
(Blanchard et al., 2001)	1998	5.3	5.2
(Pérez et al., 2001)	1998	4.1	4.1
(Stevens et al., 2003)	2002	42.0	41.5
(Baran and Oleszczuk, 2003)	2002	11.9	9.0
(Blanchard et al., 2004)	2000	23.5	22.3
(Vácha et al., 2005)	2002	9.9	8.5
	2001	5.9	6.2
(Busetti et al., 2006)	2002	1.35	1.35
(Villar et al., 2006)	2005	7.3	7.0
(Sánchez-Brunete et al., 2007)	2006	2.2	1.4
(Salihoglu et al., 2010)	2008	6.1	5.3
(Tavazzi et al., 2012)	2011	4.9	3.3
(Alhafez et al., 2013)	2012	0.54	-
(Suciu et al., 2015)	2010	0.30	0.26
	2011	0.60	0.39
	2012	0.52	0.38
	2013	0.39	0.37
(Boruszko, 2017)	2016	0.69	0.69
(Roskosch and Heidecke, 2018)	2006	6.64	
(Sørmo et al., 2024)	2021	0.99	0.98

11 Contaminant concentrations in BBF-amended soils

Concentrations of $\Sigma 7\text{PCBs}$ (left) and $\Sigma 44\text{PFAS}$ (right) in soil samples from control plots (or pre-trial soils for Austria) and BBF-amended plots. Application rates of BBFs in the field trials were 19.2 t ha^{-1} for PLP, 1.6 t kg ha^{-1} for EPH, and 1.70 t ha^{-1} for OPU.

12 Prediction of contaminant accumulation in amended soils

The contaminant concentration in SewSludge-BBFs expected in n years, $C_{cont,BBF,t=n}$ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), is given by:

$$C_{cont,BBF,t=n} = C_{cont,BBF,t=0} * 2^{-t/x} \quad (3)$$

with:

- $C_{cont,BBF,t=0}$ is the average concentration of contaminant in SewSludge-BBFs at $t=0$, i.e., average measured in this study:
 - 8.45 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PFOS (Σ concentration PFOS and PFOS precursors)
 - 6.50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PCBs
 - 2.45 ng TEQ kg^{-1} for PCDD/Fs
 - 1.29 mg kg^{-1} for PAHs
- x is the half-life of contaminants in BBFs (10, 15 and 20 years for the presented scenarios)

Then, the accumulated contaminants in amended soil after n year, $C_{cont,soil,t=n}$, is given by:

$$C_{cont,soil,t=n} = C_{cont,soil,t=0} + \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{m_{BBF}}{m_{soil}} C_{cont,BBF,t=n} \quad (4)$$

with:

- $C_{cont,soil,t=0}$ is the initial concentration in soils at $t=0$, for example median background concentrations:
 - 2.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PFOS (Brusseau et al., 2020)
 - 2.9 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PCBs (Meijer et al., 2003)
 - 3.18 ng TEQ kg^{-1} for (Vives et al., 2008)
 - 0.37 kg^{-1} for PAHs (Nam et al., 2008)
- m_{BBF} is the average mass of BBF applied per hectare annually (4.4 tons; average application rate for SewSludge-BBFs).
- m_{soil} is the average mass of soil amended per hectare (3900 tons; 30 cm of soil with density of 1.3 g cm^{-3}).

Accumulation in topsoil when $C_{cont,soil,t=0}$ equals the median background concentrations

- 2.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PFOS (Brusseau et al., 2020)
- 2.9 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for PCBs (Meijer et al., 2003)
- 3.18 ng TEQ kg^{-1} for (Vives et al., 2008)
- 0.37 kg^{-1} for PAHs (Nam et al., 2008)

Temporal decrease of POP concentrations in BBFs, half life: — 20 years - - - 15 years 10 years

13 Impact of contaminant degradation on the predicted accumulation

When temporal decrease of contaminant concentration in BBFs has a half-life of 10 years:

When temporal decrease of contaminant concentration in BBFs has a half-life of 15 years:

When temporal decrease of contaminant concentration in BBFs has a half-life of 20 years:

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